

Introducing the Physical Features of the Mazari Industrial Heritage of Zahraei in Yazd

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Abstract

The use of plants as traditional medicine in Iran is a long-standing practice. Across different regions, depending on the climate and local conditions, specific tools, facilities, and spatial arrangements have historically been developed to support this practice. In Yazd, a desert region located in central Iran, the profession of mazari (henna processing and production) has existed for generations. However, this craft and the knowledge surrounding it are now on the verge of disappearing.

This paper examines a traditional mazari workshop in Yazd as a case study in order to identify and analyze its architectural and spatial characteristics within the framework of Iran's industrial heritage. The research method is interpretive-historical, utilizing archival analysis, library studies, and fieldwork.

This study aims to determine the historical period of construction of mazari workshops, their ownership patterns, spatial organization, and architectural capabilities. The findings show that the Zahraei Henna Workshop (Hannasazi Zahraei) was established during the First Pahlavi era by the Joshon-Abazari family. The site includes distinct spaces such as the main workshop, separate storage areas for first- and second-grade henna, and a henna retail area. Due to the alignment between its architectural form and functional use throughout its lifespan, this workshop qualifies as an example of traditional industry and can be protected under the category of industrial heritage in Iran.

Keywords: mazari; henna processing; restoration; industrial heritage

1. Introduction

The use of plants for treating common and endemic illnesses, as well as their application in various proto-industrial processes, has long been recognized as an established Iranian tradition with deep historical roots. The city of Yazd, located on the margins of Iran's central deserts, has historically relied on locally available natural plants due to its harsh climatic conditions, the prevalence of climate-related diseases, its considerable distance from major medical and industrial centers, and its limited access to clean and sufficient water and essential food resources. Consequently, Yazd has held a distinguished position in utilizing indigenous plants, both for medicinal purposes and for traditional industrial production.

Among the craft communities of Yazd, "*mazārān*" locally known as *hannāsāyān* due to their principal engagement in the processing and production of henna, constitute one of the oldest groups involved in the preparation and refinement of medicinal and industrial plant materials. Their work has continued across generations, preserving the knowledge of this traditional craft.¹ The Industrial Revolution (1750–1850) in England, which later spread to other countries, brought about a complex set of technological, industrial, economic, and social transformations.² This shift, marking the emergence of an industry-based economy in place of agriculture- and labor-based production, laid the foundations for profound intellectual, political, philosophical, and legal changes. Historians therefore regard the Industrial Revolution as one of the most significant turning points in world history. Although its early impacts were limited, traditional and manual craftsmen continued to work alongside new technologies and even benefited from them in some cases.³

Prior to the Industrial Revolution, "industry" in Iran referred to small-scale workshop activities such as pottery, carpet weaving, textile production, and structures dependent on renewable energy sources, such as water canals and mills. These activities were limited in scale and fundamentally different from the mass-production industries of industrialized nations. With the rise of the Qajar dynasty in the late nineteenth century, the initial processes of industrialization in Iran emerged, gaining significant momentum during the Pahlavi period.⁴

Today, *industrial architectural heritage* refers to structures and complexes that once served industrial functions but are no longer active. These include factories, workshops, mills, industrial compounds, power and water treatment facilities, and infrastructural sites related to communication and transportation.⁵ Within this framework, mazari workshops, due to their production of henna, spices, and plant-based dyes, can be considered a form of Iran's early industrial heritage. Their development and evolution were directly affected by the arrival of new industrial technologies in the country.

2. Geographical Context of the Site

Mazari Alley is located within the Ābshāhī neighborhood of Yazd, along Ayatollah Kashani Street. This street connects to Imam Jafar Sadeq Street in the north and to Basij Boulevard in the south (Figures 1 and 3). The development of the Ābshāhī neighborhood began in 1306 SH (1927 CE), during the early Pahlavi period. Consequently, the area is situated outside the historic core of Yazd and lies beyond the boundaries of the UNESCO-designated World Heritage zone. Due to its relatively recent urban fabric compared to the historic district, the neighborhood contains fewer architecturally or culturally prominent landmarks. Among the

notable elements present are: Atabek Mosque, Farrokhi Yazdi Library, the Museum of Light, Haft-Tir Park, and Yazd University of Art and Architecture.

The Mazari Cultural and Artistic Passage (*Gozar-e Farhang va Honar-e Mazari*) is located at the beginning of Ayatollah Kashani Street, before Si'om-e Kashani Street. The Zahraei Mazari Complex, situated on Mazari Alley, has been officially recognized since 1397 SH (2018 CE) under the name “Cultural and Artistic Passage.” It lies on the eastern side of the alley and is the fourth mazari workshop within this sequence (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Location of the Ābshāhī neighborhood within the city of Yazd (Google Earth, 2021)

Figure 2.Right: Location of the Zahraei Mazari within Mazari Alley, Yazd (Google Earth, 2021). **Figure 3. Left:** Access and urban connections of Mazari Alley in Yazd (Google Earth, 2021)

3. Historical Period of Construction

Research on the historical emergence of mazari workshops and the architectural formation of their associated buildings requires further scholarly investigation. To determine the construction period and historical development of the Mazari neighborhood in its present location, two categories of documentary evidence hold particular significance:

- archival correspondence preserved in judicial records, and
- aerial photographs dating from 1335 to 1400 SH (1956–2021 CE).

The findings derived from these materials are presented in two sections.

3.1. Historical Judicial Correspondence

At the onset of municipal formation and the establishment of a public health administration in Yazd, residents submitted formal complaints regarding the operation of mazari workshops within residential areas. The primary cause of these complaints was the use of camels as the driving force for the grinding stones, which raised health concerns due to the presence of animals in close proximity to living spaces. These letters were typically addressed to the Head of the Public Health Office of Yazd, and in some cases to the Governor's Office.

Ultimately, persistent public complaints, particularly those citing the spread of fever and infection attributed to animals used in the workshops, led to an official mandate ordering the relocation of mazari workshops outside the urban fabric of Yazd. Based on the dates recorded in the available correspondence, the earliest surviving letter in the archives of the General Department of Justice in Tehran, which documents this relocation order, is dated 21 Mehr 1322 SH (October 13, 1943) (Figures 4, 5, and 6). It should be noted that the relocation directive may have been issued even earlier, but the earliest remaining documents available are from 1322 SH.

Figure 3. Right: Access and urban connections of Mazari Alley in Yaz (Google Earth, 2021). **Figure 6.** Official letter ordering the relocation of mazari workshops outside the city (National Archives of the General Department of Justice of Iran)

3.2. Aerial Photographs of Yazd (1335–1400 SH)

In addition to the aforementioned letter, another document preserved in the archival records refers to a flood event that damaged and destroyed a number of mazari buildings in their new (current) location. This indicates that the workshops in the present site were exposed to natural hazards shortly after their relocation. A review of aerial photographs of Yazd within the defined study area further clarifies the chronology of development. In the aerial imagery from 1335 SH (1956 CE), the Mazari neighborhood and the cluster of mazari workshops in their current configuration are not yet visible. For the first time, the mazari complex in its present location appears in the 1342 SH (1963 CE) aerial photographs (Figures 7 and 8).

By correlating the documentary evidence from the letters with the aerial imagery, it can be inferred that the construction of the mazari workshops and the formation of Mazari Alley in their current position along Ayatollah Kashani Street date to the late First Pahlavi period. The letters ordering the relocation of the workshops beginning in 1322 SH (1943 CE), combined with the later letter describing flood damage to the new buildings, suggest that the clustering of the workshops into a distinct neighborhood likely occurred toward the end of the First Pahlavi era (Figure 9).

Figure 7. Right: Aerial photograph of Mazari Alley, Yazd, 1400 SH (2021 CE) (Google Earth, 2021). **Figure 8.** Aerial photograph of Mazari Alley, Yazd, 1342 SH (1963 CE) (Archives of the Cultural Heritage, Handicrafts and Tourism Organization of Yazd Province).

4. Ownership of the Mazari Buildings

Based on the two sample letters presented earlier (Figures 6 and 9), it can be concluded that, prior to their relocation outside the city, mazari workshops operated on privately owned plots within the residential fabric. The same archival sources indicate that, in their new location as well, the land and buildings remained under private ownership and in the hands of mazari proprietors. At present, all mazari workshops continue to have individual, private owners. The two letters, one relating to the relocation order and the other to flood damage, show that both the responsibility for moving the workshops outside the city and the subsequent repair of the damaged buildings rested with the owners themselves.

According to an interview with the current owner of the Zahraei Mazari (Mr. Zahraei), the workshop was originally established by the Joshon-Abazari family. In 1397 SH (2018 CE), it was purchased from Mr. Joshon-Abazari (the previous owner and a member of that family). From its inception until today, the complex has remained under private ownership.

Figure 9. Archival letter documenting flood damage to several mazari buildings, dated 1322 SH (National Archives of the General Department of Justice of Iran).

5. Architectural Form and Spatial Organization of Mazari Workshops

The architectural form and spatial configuration of mazari workshops in Yazd can be understood as the result of a combined response to bioclimatic and economic factors. Mazari Alley, which accommodates the formerly scattered inner-city workshops, runs approximately in an east–west direction. On either side of the alley, each mazari occupies a rectangular plot, and in the north–south direction the workshops form a compact, dense cluster that helps to reduce solar exposure and heat gain inside the buildings.

The workshops are accessed through relatively small wooden entrance doors, often located on the southern side, followed immediately by a modest vestibule (hashti). This spatial sequence from narrow doorway to introverted interior, resembles the entrance configuration of traditional residential houses in Yazd and plays a crucial role in controlling the penetration of light, dust, and heat into the main working spaces. The thick masonry walls and the bright, mud-plastered (kāhgel) exterior surfaces reflect a significant portion of solar radiation, contributing to thermal comfort within the building. Overall, even a brief observation of the exterior of these workshops reveals how strongly their architecture has been shaped by climatic and biological requirements. Each mazari workshop accommodates at least two and at most five grinding stones (sang-e mazari). The interior space around each stone is configured as an octagonal chamber: six sides are used as storage niches for raw materials and semi-processed products, while the remaining two sides function as a passage for entry and a passage leading toward the next octagonal space where another grinding stone operates.

Above each grinding stone, whose working surface is nearly circular in plan but expressed as an octagon, a domed roof is constructed. The upper part of this dome is formed by a two-layer vault which rises to an oculus-like circular opening at the top. Above this opening, a smaller outer dome is built. Small apertures are inserted in the drum of this smaller dome to admit controlled daylight into the workshop. Ventilation in mazari buildings is provided exclusively

through the circular opening above the main dome and the small windows incorporated into the domical structure. This strategy minimizes the dispersion of henna dust throughout the interior while still facilitating air exchange. In effect, the entire ventilation system of the workshop relies on these passive architectural elements (Figures 10, 11, and 12).

Figure 10. Right: Orientation of the Zahraei Mazari relative to geographic north (Authors, 2021).
Figure 11. Left: Identification and spatial organization of different functional areas within the Zahraei Mazari(Authors, 2021).

Figure 12. Longitudinal section of the Zahraei Mazari workshop (Authors, 2021).

6. Tools and Working Equipment of Mazari Craftsmen

Despite the introduction of electricity and the replacement of animal power with electric motors, changes that have had a noticeable impact on the quality and efficiency of production, the basic tools used in mazari workshops in Yazd have remained largely unchanged. The traditional craft has preserved many of its earlier working conditions, particularly in relation to manual labor and spatial organization.

Hand tools are relatively simple and limited in variety. They include several shovels used to move henna during the grinding process, a few paddles for cleaning and gathering the powdered henna, and several metal containers placed under the sifting apparatus to collect the ground

product and facilitate its transport. Beyond these, there are few specialized tools of note. The critical “equipment” of the mazari is in fact the grinding assembly itself, which is driven by an electric motor and may be classified as a type of small-scale industrial machinery.

The main components of a typical mazari grinding unit can be described as follows (Figure 13):

Motor Track: A narrow circular track along which the motor moves at a distance of approximately 40 cm outside the perimeter of the central grinding platform (kallek), rotating around it at a speed of roughly 5–6 revolutions per minute. This track is usually paved with mosaic tiles or brick.

Kellk (Grinding Platform): A slightly elevated circular or polygonal platform relative to the motor track. Coarse henna is poured onto one side of the kallek, and after being ground beneath the upper stone, the fine powder accumulates on the opposite side.

Edge (Ledge): The edge marks the change in level between the kallek and the motor track, forming a low curb around the platform.

Lower Stone: A fixed horizontal stone embedded at the center of the kallek with a slight elevation above the platform surface.

Figure 13. Three-dimensional diagram illustrating the components of a traditional mazari grinding system (Authors, 2021).

Upper Stone: A larger, vertically rotating stone set atop the lower stone and revolving around a central vertical shaft. Generally, the upper stone is heavier and more massive than the lower one. Mazari stones typically have a service life of 20 to 30 years. After many years of operation and gradual erosion, the upper stone is often reshaped or repositioned to replace the lower stone. The craftsmen identify the stone material as rig-e jūsh (a particular dense sandstone). The price of such stones historically ranged from 800 to 1,000 tomans, whereas today they may cost up to 30,000 tomans or more.

Central Shaft (Vertical Beam): A vertical metal or timber shaft that begins within the lower stone and extends upward to connect with the overhead frame or tie-beam assembly of the roof structure.

Overhead Frame (Kalle-Sari or Tie-Beam): A pair of robust wooden beams placed parallel to one another above the grinding chamber, through which the central shaft passes before being firmly fixed to the frame.

Connecting Rod (Metal Linkage): A metal rod that is attached at one end to the central shaft via a ring-shaped clamp and, at the other end, passes through the upper stone and connects to the moving part of the motor assembly above.

Grinding Motor: The driving mechanism comprises three main elements: the motor itself, the belt, and the wheel (or tire) that runs along the motor track. Together, these components provide the rotational force that moves the upper stone around the kellek.⁶

7. Construction Materials and Architectural Treatment

In all mazari buildings, including the Zahraei Mazari, the primary construction materials are sun-dried mud-brick (khesht) for the load-bearing walls and domes, and mud plaster and gypsum for interior and exterior finishes. Stone and wood are used for the grinding apparatus and certain structural elements of the workshop.

In both the general typology of mazari buildings and the Zahraei case study, no elaborate decorative features such as wall paintings, ornamental stucco, or muqarnas are observed. This absence of applied ornament can be explained by the highly functional nature of the building and the practical difficulties that decorative elements would pose for maintenance in a dusty, industrial environment.

Figure 14. Right. Mud-plaster (kähgel) roofing and domes of the main working spaces (Authors, 2021).
Figure 15. Left. Vaulted ceilings of the storage spaces with gypsum interior finish and absence of decorative elements Source: Authors, 2021

Nevertheless, throughout the complex, we encounter architectural elements that, while primarily structural, also contribute to the spatial character of the workshop: vaulted ceilings covering storage spaces and auxiliary rooms, domes over the main grinding chambers, and

smaller exterior domes that facilitate ventilation and daylighting. Within the broader context of Iranian architecture, these forms can be regarded as a kind of inherent architectural articulation, even in the absence of additional decorative layers (Figures 14-18).

Figure 16. Exterior mud-plastered (kähgel) façade of the mazari workshop (Authors, 2021)

Figure 17. Left: Vaulted roofing system of the interior spaces of the mazari workshop (Authors, 2021)

Figure 18. Right: Vaulted ceiling and gypsum-plastered interior of the mazari workshop (Authors, 2021)

8. Conclusion

Mazari workshops were established during the First Pahlavi period under private ownership. Their architecture reflects a deliberate response to both climatic conditions and specific functional requirements associated with the processing of henna and other plant-based products. The spatial configuration and constructional features of these buildings demonstrate a strong reciprocity between physical form and function.

The internal organization of spaces, the arrangement of entrances, storage rooms for first- and second-grade henna, the courtyard, and the main grinding chambers, shows a clear hierarchy and functional logic. The central hashti of the mazari, where the grinding stones are located, is positioned between elongated storage spaces. This configuration, combined with controlled access to light and air, the deliberate absence of fragile decorative elements such as paintings and ornamental stucco, and the structurally expressive use of vaults and domes, all point to a coherent alignment between architectural form and industrial use.

A typical mazari workshop consists of:

- one or more entrances,
- storage spaces for different grades of henna,
- a courtyard, and
- one or several domed grinding chambers containing the main henna-processing equipment (the mill stones).

Due to the longstanding integration of physical and functional characteristics, these workshops can be recognized as a distinctive type within Iran's industrial architectural heritage. However, with the gradual decline of the mazari craft and the subsequent change of use in many of these buildings, a significant number of workshops have been altered, abandoned, or demolished. As a result, the authenticity and identity of the mazari as an industrial heritage typology have been compromised, particularly when the original function has been removed or replaced.

This situation underscores the urgency of documenting, conserving, and adaptively reusing such structures in ways that respect both their tangible fabric and their intangible heritage values associated with traditional plant-based industries in Yazd.

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